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Comparative analysis of microplastic pollution in commercially relevant seafood across different geographical regions

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Abstract

The pollution of the environment with plastics and derived secondary parts, microplastic, is a growing concern worldwide for animal, human and environmental health. Analysis of occurrence and characterization of the morphological and chemical characteristics of microplastics (MP) in commercially relevant species and their edible parts (flesh or muscle) are prerequisites for food risk assessment.

Despite accumulated evidence of MP contamination in different food products, it is very challenging to compare data on the same species from different studies due to the lack of standardized methods. Hence, the aim of our study was to compare MP contamination of edible parts of commercial mussels, clams and shrimps samples collected from geographically distinct markets (South Korea, Belgium, Serbia, and Croatia), thus minimizing methodological variations.

Samples (individual animal) have been subjected to an alkaline/enzymatic/oxidative digestion yielding $\geq 99.8\%$ digestion efficiency for all species analyzed. A total of 190 animals were digested individually and full chemical characterization of MPs from the whole animal on one filter by microFTIR was done. MPs were detected in 43.68 % individuals of all three commercial seafood categories analyzed (clams, mussels and shrimps) with a range of 30% (in clams from S. Korea) to 60% (in mussels from S.Korea and clams from Serbia). Average number of MPs/g edible tissue in individuals containing MPs was 1.71 ± 0.78 for clams, 1.3 ± 0.8 for mussels and 0.36 ± 0.14 for shrimps. Polystyrene and polypropylene were identified as the predominant polymer types in point-of-sale bivalves, while in shrimps, polyvinyl chloride, polyamide, and polyethylene terephthalate were found predominantly. The dominant morphologies were fragments and fibers, of size less than $150 \mu\text{m}$. For point-of-sale samples, the results of our study do not support significant MP transfer to humans by seafood.

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